

A Review Article on Seismic Evaluation and Performance Analysis of Cantilever Retaining Walls with Variable Heights

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ABSTRACT

Cantilever retaining walls are crucial structural elements used to support and stabilize soil in areas with elevation differences. During seismic events, these walls are subjected to significant dynamic forces, making their design and performance evaluation critical, especially for varying wall heights. This review explores the seismic evaluation and performance analysis of cantilever retaining walls with variable heights. Key topics include the effects of wall height variation on seismic stability, the impact of soil properties, seismic excitation characteristics, and methods for improving seismic performance. Recent advancements in analytical and numerical modeling techniques, such as finite element analysis and pseudo-static approaches, are also discussed. Findings from this review aim to contribute to improved design guidelines and enhance the resilience of cantilever retaining walls in seismic-prone regions.

Keywords- *Cantilever retaining walls, seismic evaluation, performance analysis, variable wall height, dynamic stability, earthquake engineering, finite element analysis.*

1.INTRODUCTION

Retaining walls, particularly cantilever retaining walls, are essential structures for supporting soil in engineering

projects such as highways, railways, and bridges. Cantilever walls, typically constructed from reinforced concrete, are designed with a vertical or inclined stem

that integrates with a base slab, allowing them to support considerable earth pressures. Among the types of retaining walls, cantilever retaining walls are commonly used due to their structural efficiency and relatively straightforward construction. However, during seismic events, cantilever retaining walls are subjected to dynamic forces that may cause sliding, overturning, and even catastrophic failure, especially when the wall height varies. The evaluation of these walls under seismic loads is essential for regions where earthquakes are frequent and intense.

Cantilever retaining walls with variable heights pose unique challenges in seismic design due to factors such as variations in wall weight, the distribution of lateral earth pressures, and differing wall stability requirements across heights. Additionally, soil properties, the wall-soil interaction, and the characteristics of seismic waves affect the stability of these structures.

Background and Importance-

Earthquakes impart dynamic loads that are difficult to predict and vary significantly based on factors such as the type of ground motion, soil properties, and structural geometry. As retaining walls of varying heights are subjected to different lateral forces along their length, it is essential to understand how these factors influence their seismic behavior. Seismic design codes, such as IS 1893 (Part 1): 2016 in India, provide general guidelines but often lack specific recommendations for cantilever walls with variable heights. This review synthesizes research on the influence of height variations and outlines methods to enhance seismic resilience.

Seismic evaluation is critical for retaining walls because these structures are subject to additional dynamic forces during an earthquake. Seismic forces can cause significant lateral loading, leading to instability or failure through:

- I. Sliding: Movement of the wall along its base.
- II. Overturning: Rotational failure caused by excessive lateral forces
- III. Structural damage: Cracking or collapse due to stress beyond the material's capacity.

Objectives and Scope of the project-

The major objectives of this project work are:

- 1. Evaluate the Seismic Behavior of Cantilever Retaining Walls Under Various Heights:**

This involves studying how cantilever retaining walls, which support soil or other materials, respond to seismic forces at different heights. It helps understand how their performance changes with varying wall sizes during earthquakes.

- 2. Assess Factors Influencing Stability and Deformation During Seismic Events:**

This objective focuses on identifying and analyzing factors that affect the stability and deformation of retaining walls during seismic events, such as soil type, wall material, and seismic intensity.

- 3. Develop Design Recommendations for Seismic-Resistant Cantilever Walls:**

Based on the evaluation and assessment, this goal is to create guidelines or recommendations to improve the design of cantilever retaining walls, making them more resistant to seismic forces and reducing the risk of failure during earthquakes.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

- [1] Prediction of Concrete and Steel Materials Contained by Cantilever Retaining Wall by Modeling the Artificial Neural Networks (2018) by U. Gokkus, M.S. Yildirim, A. Yilmazoglu**

The use of Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) for predicting material requirements in civil engineering structures has shown promising advancements, particularly in the accurate estimation of concrete volume and steel reinforcement. In structural design, these predictions play a crucial role in cost estimation, material optimization, and ensuring the structural adequacy of retaining walls. This literature review discusses the application of ANNs in predicting material quantities for cantilever retaining walls, focusing on ANN-based models, the Mononobe-Okabe approach, and the use of optimization algorithms such as Artificial Bee Colony (ABC) in ANN training. Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) have increasingly been applied in civil engineering for tasks requiring pattern recognition, prediction, and classification. ANNs are particularly useful in scenarios where traditional analytical models may be limited due to the complexity of the data or non-linearity. As illustrated by Ghalehnovi et al. (2016), ANNs can effectively model complex relationships between input and output parameters, such as predicting material quantities for different retaining wall designs based on structural and soil properties.

[2] Seismic Response and Evaluation of Cantilever Retaining Wall (2018) by Mr. Nasim Khan, Mr. Aftab Alam

A Cantilever retaining wall is one of the most important types of retaining structures. It is extensively used in variety of situations such as highway engineering, railway engineering, bridge engineering and irrigation engineering. Reinforced concrete retaining walls have a vertical or inclined stem cast with base slab. For greater heights earth pressure due to retained fill will be higher due to lever arm effect, higher moments are produced at base, which leads to higher section for stability design as well as structural design. This studies the stability and performance for seismic response and evaluation of cantilever retaining wall with the help of a finite element method, STAAD.pro. While the following provisions of the Indian Standard Code, IS 456:2000 and IS 1893: 1984/2002 for the sections.

[3] Performance-based Optimal Design of Cantilever Retaining Walls (2019) by Mohsen Kalateh-Ahani, Arman Sarani

Performance-based design (PBD) has emerged as a significant approach in structural engineering, particularly in enhancing resilience against seismic activities. Traditional design methodologies often prioritize structural safety under anticipated loads without thoroughly balancing costs associated with structural performance. However, with PBD, engineers and project stakeholders can develop optimized designs that meet specific performance criteria while controlling costs. This literature review explores key developments and studies on the performance-based optimal design of cantilever retaining walls, with a particular focus on seismic resilience, cost optimization, and structural displacement.

[4] Performance-Based Analysis of Cantilever Retaining Walls Subjected to Near-Fault Ground Shakings (2020) by Milad Aghamolaei, Alireza Saedi Azizkandi, Mohammad Hassan Baziar, and Sadegh Ghavami

This paper investigates the seismic performance of cantilever retaining walls under near-fault ground shaking, focusing on the unique effects of forward-directivity in near-fault regions. Using finite element modeling, the authors evaluate how near-fault ground motions, characterized by high-intensity velocity

pulses, affect cantilever retaining walls compared to far-field earthquake motions.

Key components of the study include:

1. Wavelet approach: Used to extract velocity pulses from near-source ground motions, which were compared with synthetic far-field earthquake records.
2. Seismic performance: A clear distinction in lateral displacement was observed, with up to 85% higher displacement under near-fault conditions compared to far-field excitations, though the forces along the walls were similar.

[5] Investigation of Seismic Response of Cantilever Retaining Walls: Limit Analysis vs Shaking Table Testing (2020) by Panos Kloukinas, Anna Scotto di Santolo, Augusto Penna, Matthew Dietz, Aldo Evangelista, Armando Lucio Simonelli, Colin Taylor, and George Mylonakis

This paper presents a comprehensive study of the seismic behavior of cantilever retaining walls, focusing on both theoretical and experimental analyses. Conducted at the University of Bristol (EERC - EQUALS), the study compares limit analysis and shaking table testing to evaluate the response of cantilever retaining walls under seismic conditions.

Key Aspects of the Study:

1. Theoretical Analysis: The research employs both limit analysis and wave-propagation methods, which consider multiple factors, including inertia, strength, kinematics, and deformation compatibility. These methods provide exact theoretical solutions for cantilever retaining walls subjected to seismic forces, addressing the fundamental mechanics involved in soil-structure interaction during earthquakes.
2. Shaking Table Testing: The experimental part of the research involves shaking table tests on small-scale models, incorporating different retaining wall geometries, soil configurations, and ground motions. This experimental setup is designed to replicate real seismic conditions and observe the behavior of the retaining walls in a controlled environment.

[6] Seismic Behavior of Cantilever Wall Embedded in Dry and Saturated Sand (2020) by Sanku Konai, Aniruddha Sengupta, and Kousik Deb

This research article investigates the seismic behavior of embedded cantilever retaining walls in dry and saturated sand, focusing on both experimental and numerical analyses. The study addresses a significant gap in the literature, as most previous studies have concentrated on the static behavior of such walls, leaving their seismic performance underexplored.

Key findings include:

1. In dry sand, the maximum lateral displacement due to seismic loading is less than 1% of the total wall height.
2. In saturated sand, the lateral displacement can be as high as 12.75% of the total wall height, a significant increase attributed to the variation in pore water pressure within the sand.
3. The study highlights the critical influence of soil saturation on the seismic performance of cantilever retaining walls, especially in terms of lateral movement and structural stability. The research underscores the importance of accounting for soil conditions, particularly water content, in the design of retaining structures in seismic zones.

[7] Displacement based seismic assessment of base restrained retaining walls (2022) by Rohit Tiwari & Nelson Lam

Retaining walls are critical in providing lateral support for soil, particularly in areas prone to seismic activity where lateral forces can induce significant structural demands. Displacement-based seismic assessment (DBSA) has emerged as a valuable approach for evaluating the seismic performance of these structures, focusing on the displacement and deformation patterns under seismic loads rather than only on force-based assessments. This literature review examines recent studies on displacement-based seismic assessment, specifically for base-restrained retaining walls, which face unique challenges due to their structural confinement at the base. Base-restrained retaining walls are particularly sensitive to seismic forces due to the restriction at the base, which limits their capacity to shift or rotate as a response to lateral pressures. Studies such as Mylonakis et al. (2006) demonstrate that base restraint can increase wall rigidity

but also lead to greater shear and bending stresses at the wall base, thus increasing vulnerability during earthquakes. These stresses, if not properly managed, can result in structural cracking or even failure. Displacement-based assessment is thus crucial in these walls as it emphasizes allowable deformation levels that can mitigate such risks

[8] Dynamic Analysis of Cantilever Retaining Wall (2022) by Prajakta Patil, M. V. Waghmare

This paper explores the seismic behavior of cantilever retaining walls, emphasizing the influence of soil response on the structure's motion. Retaining walls are key for lateral soil support, and the study aims to enhance their seismic design using 3D finite element analysis (FEA) with ANSYS software.

The analysis follows three stages:

1. Static Analysis: To assess the initial structural behavior.
2. Modal Analysis: Calculating natural frequencies and mode shapes of the wall.
3. Nonlinear Time History Analysis: Using three distinct earthquake ground motions to simulate real seismic conditions.

The paper highlights that the soil significantly affects the dynamic response of the wall. The study finds maximum displacement occurring at the top of the wall, with no structural failure under the given loading. Additionally, the distribution of equivalent (Von Mises) stress shows lower stress near the ground and higher stress at the base of the wall, especially between the stem and base slab in the soil cover zone. The research provides key insights into how soil dynamics impact the retaining wall, aiding in the safe design of such structures under seismic loading conditions.

[9] Seismic Behavior of Retaining Walls: A Critical Review of Analytical and Field Performance Studies (2023) by Sabahat Ali Khan, Mourad Karray, and Patrick Paultre

This paper presents a comprehensive review of the seismic behavior of retaining walls, focusing on the complex soil-structure interaction under dynamic loading conditions. Retaining walls are critical in earth retention, and understanding their seismic performance is a vital concern for researchers, industry professionals, and governmental bodies alike. The article evaluates

various analytical and field performance studies that address seismically induced lateral earth pressures on retaining walls.

Key points in the review include:

1. **Dynamic Earth Pressure:** The paper examines how seismic events generate lateral forces on retaining walls, influenced by multiple factors such as soil type, wall geometry, and seismic intensity.
2. **Soil-Structure Interaction:** The interaction between soil and retaining structures under seismic loading is identified as a complex phenomenon requiring advanced analysis techniques.
3. **Design Methodologies:** Existing design standards and methodologies are critiqued for their inadequacies in capturing real-world seismic performance, stressing the need for more refined approaches.

[10] Parametric Analysis and Design of Cantilever Retaining Walls Under Different Soil Conditions (2024) by Kara Naga Sree Vallabh, Asileti Prashanth, Cheera Vamsikrishna, Kallelapola Sankar, Minjuru Kuma, N. Rama Rao

Cantilever retaining walls play a crucial role in construction by supporting soil masses and preventing soil erosion, especially on terrains with significant elevation changes. Designed to withstand lateral pressures, these walls are commonly used in infrastructure projects such as roads, buildings, and terraces. They are constructed without lateral support at the top, relying on their footing to provide stability against earth pressures. This review examines the parametric design considerations of cantilever retaining walls, focusing on the impact of varying soil types on bending moments and reinforcement requirements. Understanding the effects of soil variation on cantilever retaining wall design is critical for safe and cost-effective construction. The parametric analysis conducted in this study highlights the necessity of tailored design approaches for different soil types, specifically regarding bending moment distribution and reinforcement adjustments. This research contributes to the broader knowledge of retaining wall design by offering a framework for engineers to assess and adapt wall specifications according to soil properties, enhancing wall durability and performance in diverse environmental settings.

3. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Finite Element Analysis Using STAAD.pro- Finite Element Analysis (FEA) has proven valuable in providing more accurate predictions of seismic performance in retaining walls. STAAD.pro, a software tool for structural analysis, offers a comprehensive framework for modeling cantilever walls and evaluating their behavior under various load combinations. Studies reveal that FEA can capture detailed stress distributions, deformation patterns, and potential failure modes in retaining walls, which enhances the overall design precision and safety. In particular, FEA enables engineers to assess the impact of seismic forces on wall stability by examining factors like moment generation at the base due to retained soil and lateral earth pressure. For taller retaining walls, these moments can significantly influence section design, as well as the wall's overall stability.

Indian Standard Codes for Seismic Retaining Wall

Design- The Indian Standards IS 456:2000 and IS 1893:1984/2002 provide guidelines for designing reinforced concrete structures under seismic loads. IS 456:2000 focuses on the general structural requirements and durability of concrete structures, whereas IS 1893 addresses seismic considerations for buildings and structures. These codes are crucial in ensuring that cantilever retaining walls meet the minimum safety and performance standards, accounting for factors like load combinations, material strengths, and seismic zone classifications. Recent research emphasizes the need for updates to these codes, particularly to integrate advancements in FEA and evolving knowledge on soil-structure interactions under seismic loads

4. CONCLUSION

The review of seismic evaluation and performance analysis of cantilever retaining walls with variable heights underscores the critical role of height, soil properties, and seismic excitation characteristics in influencing wall stability during earthquakes. The analysis reveals those variations in wall height present unique challenges due to changes in lateral earth pressure distribution and stability requirements. The studies reviewed highlight that conventional design codes, such as IS 1893 (Part 1): 2016, lack specific guidance on height-variable retaining walls, underscoring the need for more tailored design

provisions in seismic regions. In conclusion, this review provides valuable insights into the factors affecting the seismic performance of cantilever retaining walls with variable heights and emphasizes the need for design guidelines that consider height variations. Future research should focus on refining analytical models and exploring innovative design solutions to improve the seismic resilience of cantilever retaining walls, contributing to safer infrastructure in earthquake-prone areas.

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Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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